

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART X. STUDIES ON THE ADSORPTION OF Cu^{++} AND FeCy_6^{++++} IONS BY COPPER FERROCYANIDE SOL, AND THE EFFECT OF DILUTION ON THE COMPOSITION OF COPPER FERROCYANIDE

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Composition of the copper ferrocyanide sol has been studied from the adsorption of Cu^{++} and FeCy_6^{++++} ions. Influence of hydrolysis and adsorption on the composition of the compound has been confirmed.

In continuation of the physico-chemical studies on the composition of copper ferrocyanide (Bhattacharya and Gaur, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 487, 499 ; 1948, 25, 27) the adsorption of Cu^{++} and FeCy_6^{++++} ions by copper ferrocyanide sol, and also the effect of dilution on the sol have been studied, in order to throw further light on the composition and behaviour of copper ferrocyanide. Influence of hydrolysis and adsorption on the composition of the compound has been confirmed by experimental results.

EXPERIMENTAL

Adsorption Experiments.—Copper ferrocyanide sol (25 g/litre) was prepared by mixing copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide solutions in the molar ratio of 1 : 1. The sols prepared in other ratios were unstable, and so were the sols of higher concentrations.

For carrying out the adsorption experiments, the sols were dialysed for 7 to 8 days when the amount of free FeCy_6^{++++} in the dialysate was almost negligible. In order to study the adsorption of FeCy_6^{++++} , 50 c.c. of the dialysed sol were taken and mixed with equal volumes of $M/20$, $M/25$, $M/40$, $M/50$, $M/80$, $M/100$ potassium ferrocyanide solutions in different glass cylinders. In each case the contents were mixed up well, and coagulated by addition of A. R. ammonium sulphate, and the equilibrium concentration of potassium ferrocyanide was determined volumetrically by titrating against standardised solution of potassium permanganate. A blank reading with 50 c. c. of the sol, and an equal volume of water was also taken, and the readings in other cases were corrected for this ferrocyanide, which was originally present in the sol for its stability. From the initial and equilibrium concentrations of potassium ferrocyanide, the amount of K_4FeCy_6 adsorbed per g. of the complex was calculated. The adsorption of Cu^{++} ions was carried out in a similar way. Cu^{++} was estimated by iodometry.

TABLE I

Adsorption of Cu⁺⁺ by copper ferrocyanide sol.

(cf. Fig. 1)

Conc. of CuSO ₄ added (after correcting for stabilising FeCy ₆ ^{'''})	Equilib. conc.	CuSO ₄ adsorbed per g. of the complex. (x/m)
1 7.781 g./litre	7.122 g./litre	1.61 m. moles
2 6.809	5.809	1.48
3 3.814	3.332	1.21
4 2.950	2.554	1.01
5 2.4757	2.120	0.95

FIG. 1
*Adsorption of Cu⁺⁺ by copper
ferrocyanide sol.*

FIG. 2
*Adsorption of FeCy₆^{'''} by
copper ferrocyanide sol.*

TABLE II

Adsorption of FeCy₆^{'''} by copper ferrocyanide sol.

(cf. Fig 2)

Conc. of K ₄ FeCy ₆ (after correcting for the stabilising FeCy ₆ ^{'''}).	Equilib. conc.	K ₄ FeCy ₆ adsorbed per g. of the complex.
1 18.8938 g./litre	18.3221 g./litre	0.92 m. moles
2 14.8395	14.3082	0.68
3 12.4485	11.9687	0.52
4 9.4065	9.0602	0.44
5 5.9345	6.0033	0.36
6 4.7145	4.5529	0.17

Effect of Dilution on the Sol.—Samples of the sols dialysed for 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 days were prepared, the volume in each case was made the same so that the concentration of the sol in each case was 2.5 g./litre of the complex. The undialysed and the dialysed sols were diluted, and FeCy_6^{+++} released by the original, and twice, thrice, and four times diluted sols on coagulation was determined by titrating against standard potassium permanganate. The concentration of released FeCy_6^{+++} was so low that the usual method of deHaën for its estimation by titrating against very dilute potassium permanganate was found to be unreliable. The end-point was detected by adding excess of $N/400$ potassium permanganate, and back titrating the residual excess against $N/400$ potassium ferrocyanide, potentiometrically. A bright platinum foil was used as an indicator electrode, in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. The end-point was detected by a sudden fall in the value of dE/dc and it was very sharp. The amount of FeCy_6^{+++} released per g. of the complex was calculated as K_4FeCy_6 . Results are given below.

TABLE III

Copper ferrocyanide sol (1 : 1).

(Strength = 2.5 g./litre)

(cf. Fig. 3)

Conc. of the sol.	Equiv. vol. of $N/400$ K_4FeCy_6 for 20 c.c. of supernatant layer.	K_4FeCy_6 per litre of the supernatant layer (m./moles)	K_4FeCy_6 released per g. of the sol. (m./moles)
Undialysed sol.			
A/1	7.3 c.c.	9.125×10^{-1}	0.345
A/2	4.1	5.125	0.410
A/3	2.95	3.689	0.442
A/4	2.25	2.812	0.450
Sol dialysed for 1 day.			
A/1	6.1	7.625	0.305
A/2	3.2	4.00	0.32
A/3	2.3	2.75	0.33
A/4	1.8	2.25	0.36
Sol dialysed for 2 days.			
A/1	5.1	6.375	0.255
A/2	2.7	3.375	0.270
A/3	1.9	2.375	0.285
A/4	1.5	1.812	0.300
Sol dialysed for 3 days.			
A/1	4.1	5.125	0.205
A/2	2.2	2.750	0.220
A/3	1.55	1.938	0.232
A/4	1.30	1.625	0.260
Sol dialysed for 4 days.			
A/1	3.7	4.625	0.185
A/2	1.9	2.375	0.190
A/3	1.3	1.625	0.195
A/4	1.0	1.250	0.200

DISCUSSION

The accompanying curves (Fig. 3) show that the release of FeCy_6'''

FIG. 3

Effect of dilution on copper ferrocyanide sol.

per g. of the complex is much greater in the undialysed sol. The proportional increase of FeCy_6''' on dilution is also greater in the undialysed sol than when dialysed. Gradual release of FeCy_6''' on dilution suggests that the sol suffers hydrolysis to some extent, as otherwise the concentration of the released FeCy_6''' per g. on dilution and precipitation of the sol would have been almost constant.

In the study of the composition of copper ferrocyanide by physico-chemical methods (Bhattacharya and Gaur, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 487, 499; 1948, 25 27) it was observed by us that the composition of the complex suffered a change from its normal formula due to combined effects of hydrolysis and adsorption. The observations of adsorption of Cu'' and FeCy_6''' ions by copper ferrocyanide sol and also its effect of dilution support the view advanced by us.